

Correlation of Aerosol Particles with Clouds and Radiation Budget Over East Africa-Ethiopia Using MODIS Satellite Data: Part 02

Ambachew Abeje Alemu^{a,b} and Jaya Prakash Raju^a

^aPhysics Department, Since College, Bahir Dar University, Bahir Dar, 6000, Amhara Regional State, Ethiopia

^bPhysics Department, Science College, Debre Tabor University, Debre Tabor, 6300, Amhara Regional State, Ethiopia

Correspondence: ambnehabe21@gmail.com(AA. Alemu) and lidarraju@gmail.com(JP. Raju)

Abstract. The aerosol particles are positively associated with the cloud parameters, precipitation and radiation budgets. The correlations of the aerosols-clouds-precipitations interaction ACPI are uncertain, that show large spatiotemporal variability in their magnitude. For this study, the aerosol particles and clouds data were retrieved from the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer MODIS sensors. These comprised of aerosol optical depth AOD, Ångström exponential AET, atmospheric water vapor AWV, mean cloud fraction CFM, cloud top pressure CTP and cloud top temperature CTT. The precipitation data is comprised of 3B43 monthly products sourced from Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission TRMM and the outgoing long-wave radiation OLR flux is comprised of Clouds and Earth's Radiant Energy System CERES satellite instruments.

The study covers sixteen sites in East Africa-Ethiopia with neighbouring Eritrea, Djibouti, and South Sudan countries clustered into four regions for the periods 2001–2022 to provide detailed information on the aerosol particles spatiotemporal correlations on clouds and precipitation. The increase-decrease AET, AWV, CFM and PPT fluctuations are with AOD opposing OLR, CTP and CTT. The spatial correlations are oriented towards western part mostly in southwest of the study area regions. The clustered regions show minima radiative forcing in 2012 at the southwest cluster for all F_{Surf} and at the southeast cluster for F_{TOA} , with their maxima at the northwest cluster in 2022 for F_{Surf} and in 2010 for F_{TOA} from both instruments. Accordingly, the minimum values are -23.83 and 8.37 for Terra and -22.95 and 7.68 for Aqua, and the maxima are -0.58 and 63.80 for Terra and -1.37 and 58.83 for Aqua, respectively. Here, the values for all of the parameters we observed in the Terra satellite are mostly greater than those of the Aqua satellite. The values for the parameters were higher in the southern clusters, specifically in the southwest clusters, than in the northern clusters.

The mean cloud fraction CFM was less dominant, while AET was the most dominant variable with $0.02733 < \beta_1 < 15.17547$ in the regression analysis. The study area regions showed the best performance values, with $0.93941 < R < 0.99958$ for all the seasons. The minimum values observed in Bega at Kombolcha are from Aqua for both β_1 and R, while their maximums are from Terra in Kiremt at Bahir Dar for the dominance and in Tseday at Agnuak for the performance we described.

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1 Introduction

Our planet Earth consists of the atmosphere, hydrosphere, cryosphere, land surface and biosphere. It is a complex system of interacting physical, chemical and biological processes that provides a natural laboratory whose experiments have been running since the beginning of time. The gaseous part above the Earth's surface includes traces of other gaseous, liquid and solid substances. Its weather, radiation balance, formation of clouds and precipitation, atmospheric flow, reservoir of natural and anthropogenic trace gases, transport of heat, water vapour, tracers, dust and aerosols (Shrestha and Singh, 2014; Kafle and Coulter, 2013; Grythe, 2017).

Aerosols are tiny mixes of particulate materials suspended in the atmosphere that consist of both liquid droplets and solid particles. They influence the Earth's radiation budget and hence climate change by directly scattering and absorbing solar radiation and indirectly by acting as cloud condensation nuclei CCN, altering cloud properties and precipitation. Particles of atmospheric aerosols greatly affect the Earth's radiation budget and cloud characteristics. So that in addition to their radiative effects, aerosol particles act as condensation nuclei for cloud CCN and ice IN formation and can therefore affect precipitation in several ways (Kafle and Coulter, 2013; Jia et al., 2019; hu).

The aerosol particles that are injected directly into the atmosphere through natural and anthropogenic sources are known as 'primary aerosols'. These include sea spray, biomass burning, incomplete combustion of fossil fuels, volcanic eruptions, wind-driven or traffic-related suspension of the road, soil, mineral dust, sea salt, sand, and biological materials. Secondary aerosol particles are emitted in another form and then become aerosol particles after going through chemical reactions in the atmosphere, such as sulphate aerosols from volcanoes or industrial emissions. All aerosols can also undergo further chemical changes, referred to as 'aging effects'. They have numerous potential feedback processes that are still poorly understood, making them an essential component of the atmospheric hydrological cycle and its radiation budget (Chi et al., 2019; Wild and Liepert, 2010; Behera, 2016; Gaffney et al., 2006).

Studies indicated that aerosol particles positively constellated with cloud parameters and radiation budget. There is also clear and rapidly growing evidence that atmospheric aerosol particles have profound impacts on the thermodynamics and radiative energy budgets of the Earth. The aerosol particles affect the atmosphere: directly by altering the properties of the radiation energy budget through scattering and absorbing the solar radiation; indirectly by affecting the cloud micro-physical properties; and semi-directly through the absorbed radiation energy by aerosol particles, which is able to increase the temperature of the surrounding air, resulting in the evaporation of cloud droplets and ice particles (Myhre et al., 2013; Kafle and Coulter, 2013) (Myhre et al., 2013; Li et al., 2021; Kaufman et al., 2000; Andreae and Rosenfeld, 2008).

The aerosol particles-cloud parameters-precipitation interactions attract more attention, so regional as well as global scientific observations are needed to qualify and confirm the situations. From a previous literature review, we found that there are few studies on atmospheric aerosol particles optical properties in East Africa-Ethiopia using ground or satellite data (Homa et al., 2017; Getachew, 2009; Eshet and Raju, 2022). However, to date, no one has reported the correlation of aerosol particles with cloud parameters and radiation budget using satellite data from the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer MODIS, Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission TRMM, and Clouds and Earth's Radiant Energy System CERES.

60 The MODIS is a key instrument that consists of Terra and Aqua satellites onboard that provide long-term and continuous measurement of different aerosol properties from a very long time and plays important role in validating and developing new models to predict climate change (Pagano and Durham, 1993; Ismael, 2015; Deep et al., 2021; Koukouli et al., 2010). The Terra satellite orbits around the Earth during the morning at 10:30 local time, descending in the north-to-south direction, while Aqua orbits during the afternoon at 13:30 local time, ascending in the south-to-north direction (Levy et al., 2018; Ustin and
65 Middleton, 2021; Liu et al., 2021). Both of these instruments capture the same area on the Earth with 36 spectral bands that can observe its surface every 1–2 days (Bekker et al., 2014; Verma et al., 2019; Justice et al., 1998).

The TRMM is a joint space mission in between the National Aeronautics and Space Administration NASA and Japan's National Space Development Agency NASDA of Japan which is designed to monitor and study tropical and subtropical precipitation and the associated release of energy. By covering the tropical and subtropical regions of the Earth, the TRMM provided important
70 precipitation information using several space-borne instruments to increase our understanding of the interactions between water vapor, clouds, and precipitation that are central to regulating Earth's climate (Maggioni et al., 2016; Theon, 1994; Simpson et al., 1988).

The CERES is a key component of the Earth Observing System EOS, Suomi National Polar-Orbiting Partnership S-NPP, and National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration NOAA-20 observatories. It also consists of Terra and Aqua satellites with
75 a three-channel radiometer: a shortwave channel, a long-wave channel, and a total channel that measures both solar-reflected radiation at the top of the atmosphere and Earth-emitted radiation from the Earth's surface (Smith et al., 2011; Parkinson, 2022; Loeb et al., 2018).

Hence, in this study, we used the climatological database of the aerosol particles optical properties, namely the aerosol optical depth AOD and Ångström Exponent AET (Toledano et al., 2007; B. AL-Taie et al., 2020; Kumar et al., 2015), and the cloud
80 parameters such as atmospheric water vapor AWV, the mean cloud fraction CFM, cloud top pressure CTP, and cloud top temperature CTT (Sporre, 2016; Barthlott and Hoose, 2018) from MODIS, the precipitation PPT (Barthlott and Hoose, 2018; Li et al., 2017) from TRMM, and the out going long-wave radiation OLR flux (Myhre et al., 2013; Li et al., 2017) from CERES satellite instruments, to identify the interactions over East Africa-Ethiopia.

2 Materials and Analysis Methods

85 This section outlines the research areas and locations selected for the effects of aerosol particles, along with the data source. In addition, this section includes the methods used in this study to fill in the gaps left by other findings from previous work.

2.1 The Study Areas and Sites

This research was carried out in East Africa, more specifically in Ethiopia. Even though they became independent daughter countries, Djibouti and Eritrea which were parts of Ethiopia formerly, and also South Sudan were purposefully incorporated
90 into the study areas of the research (Negash, 2019; Dias, 2013; Tongco, 2007). Sixteen sites, i.e., ten from Ethiopia, three from South Sudan, two from Eritrea, and one from Djibouti, were selected and then divided into four clustered regions: southwest,

southeast, northwest and northeast. Figure 1 shows four East African countries, namely Ethiopia, Eritrea, Djibouti and South Sudan{3–18° N, 24–48° E} which have been taken as the study areas{1,897,129 km²} of this research, along with details of those sites in their clustered regions. Generally, the study areas and selected sites consist of both the continental and maritime aerosol particles sources.

2.2 Remote Sensing Data

Remote sensing is the process of obtaining information about objects, areas, or phenomena from a distance without being in physical contact. It includes the use of satellite or aircraft-based sensor technologies to detect and classify objects on the Earth's surface and in the atmosphere and oceans (Roughgarden et al., 1991; Silleos, 2000). The high spatial and temporal resolution of satellite remote sensing data is more valuable in most atmospheric sciences studies. Such measurements are made using different platform sensor configurations (Freemantle et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2022; Briffa et al., 2020). For this study, we used monthly data obtained at the web portals: MODIS <https://ladsweb.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov/search/order/> to retrieve aerosol particles and cloud parameters; CERES <https://asdc.larc.nasa.gov/data/CERES/ES4/> to calculate outgoing long-wave flux; and TRMM https://daac.gsfc.nasa.gov/datasets/TRMM_3B43_7/summary?keywords=TRMM_3B43_7 to find the precipitation. Particularly, we collected the data for the Terra satellites MOD08_M3–61 and Terra-Xtrk_Edition4 from January 2001–December 2022, and for TRMM_3B43 from January 1998–December 2019, all for a period of 264 months, and for the Aqua satellite MYD08_3M–61 and Aqua-Xtrk_Edition4 from July 2002–December 2022 for a period of 246 months.

2.3 Satellite Data Retrieval

After the daily HDF dataset had been browsed from the MODIS website, the aerosol particles parameters optical properties like the AOD and AET were calculated using MATLAB codes. This subsection is to describe the methods we had been using to derive the details for both the parameters AOD and AET optical properties retrievals from the MODIS satellite datasets.

The parameter aerosol optical depth AOD is the measure of the turbidity-opacity of an environment or a medium (Chen et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2021; LeBlanc et al., 2020). The optical parameter AOD describes section of light removed from a beam by scattering and absorption during its path through the environment (Jin et al., 2023). The AOD values that depend on the sizes, shapes, numbers, concentrations, and the indexes of refraction of the aerosol particles, which are related to the wavelength by using the equation as (Symeonidis, 2017):

$$AOD(\lambda) = \ln\left(\frac{\phi_e^i, \lambda}{\phi_e^t, \lambda}\right) = \ln(T_\lambda) \quad (1)$$

where:

- 120 ϕ_e^i, λ is the spectral radiant flux in wavelength received;
- ϕ_e^t, λ is the spectral radiant flux in wavelength transmitted;
- T_λ is the spectral transmittance in wavelength λ .

Typically, the AOD($0.55\mu\text{m}$) ranges from 0.05 to 1 over the remote ocean, to 2.0 or even 5.0 during the time of heavy pollution, smoke and dust (B. AL-Taie et al., 2020; Patel and Application, 2016). For AOD values x_i , the mean \bar{x} could be calculated as follows (Hopkins and Weeks, 1990):

$$\bar{x} = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{x_i}{n} \right). \quad (2)$$

So, the standard deviation S_d is given by:

$$S_d = \sqrt{\sum_1^n \left(\frac{x_i - \bar{x}}{n} \right)}. \quad (3)$$

And the coefficient of variance CV in % is:

$$CV(\%) = \frac{S_d}{\bar{x}} \times 100\%. \quad (4)$$

The parameter Ångström exponent AET is one of the basic parameters that widely used in atmospheric sciences dealing with the optical properties of aerosol particles. This optical parameter is treated as the indirect measure of the aerosol size in a given column of air. Given the turbidity coefficient β , then AET had been calculated from the AOD values using (Thapa et al., 2016):

$$AOD(\lambda) = \beta \lambda^{-AET} \text{ and then,} \quad (5)$$

$$AET = \frac{\ln(AOD) - \ln(\beta)}{\ln(\lambda)}.$$

2.4 The Correlation Analysis

When two or more quantities vary in sympathy so that movements in one tend to be accompanied by corresponding movements in the others, then they are said to be correlated. The correlation can be positive or negative, and it shows the direction and degree of relationship between the variables (Senthilnathan, 2019; Gogtay and Thatte, 2017; Tang et al., 2020). Let P be an m x n matrix of daily data, where m is the number of days and n is the number of stations. This matrix can be decomposed into linear functions of m temporal and n spatial vectors so that the observation P_{ij} on day i at station j is given by (Stephenson et al., 1999; Gitau et al., 2013; Ledesma and Valero-Mora, 2019):

$$P_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n a_{ik} e_{jk}, \quad P = \sum P_{ij} = ae \quad (6)$$

where a_{ik} is the element for day i in k^{th} time vector and e_{jk} the element for station j in k^{th} space vector.

The standardized dataset (A_{ij}) and symmetric n x n correlation matrix C are given as:

$$A_{ij} = \frac{P_{ij} - \bar{P}_{ij}}{S_d} \text{ and } C = \frac{A'A}{m-1} \quad (7)$$

The eigenvectors e are space vectors and the corresponding eigenvalues λ are measures of the explained variance accounted for each eigenvector. Decomposition of correlation matrix into eigenvectors e , and associated eigenvalues λ are obtained by solving:

$$(C - \lambda I)e = 0, \quad |(C - \lambda I)| = 0 \quad (8)$$

Given a $p \times m$ matrix, $U_m = (u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_m)$ of the significance correlated data loadings. Simplifying with rotation can be achieved by seeking an $m \times m$ rotation matrix R to construct the rotation of the empirical orthogonal functions REOFs K according to (Hansen et al., 2008; Zambreski, 2016);

$$K = U_m \beta \quad (9)$$

Maximum factor loadings after rotation that is the correlation coefficients between the variables and factors will be used to determine the relation of selected variables, the parameters for the aerosol optical properties, clouds and precipitations. The simplicity criterion for choosing the rotation matrix for maximization problem is expressed by:

$$\max f(U_m \beta). \quad (10)$$

160 2.5 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Determination of the combined effect of aerosol particles and clouds on precipitation utilized a multiple linear regression MLR analysis. MLR analysis is to determine which variable in a set of variables is the best predictor of an outcome. The MLR first-order models are given as (Ahmad et al., 2019; Abdullah et al., 2017; Ngaina, 2015):

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{1i} + \beta_2 x_{2i} + \beta_3 x_{3i} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ki} + \epsilon_i \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{B}_k = [\mathbf{1} \ \mathbf{X}_{ki}] \backslash [\mathbf{Y}_i - \epsilon_i] \quad (11)$$

165 where:

Y_i is the value of the response variable in the i^{th} observation;

β_k is the slope parameter associated with the k^{th} variable;

β_0 is the intercept parameter;

170 x_{ki} is the k^{th} independent variable associated with the i^{th} observation;

ϵ_i is the random error term with mean $E(\epsilon_i) = 0$ and variance $\sigma^2(\epsilon_i) = \sigma^2$.

In MLR analysis, the least squares method is used to find a function that fits a given data. The method minimizes the sum of the n squared errors SSE of the observed values y_i and the predicted values on the fitted line \hat{y}_i .

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (12)$$

175 The variable inflation factors VIFs measure the impact of the collinearity on the standard errors of the estimate variables. The square root of VIF shows the inflation of standard error by the other variables in the model. The VIF for each independent

variable can be computed as follows (Young et al., 2008; Ostertagová, 2012):

$$VIF_k = (1 - R_k^2)^{-1} \quad (13)$$

Akaike information criterion AIC measures the relative quality of the statistical model for a given set of data with tradeoffs between complexity and goodness of fit of model. AIC statistic is calculated as:

$$AIC = n \ln \left(\frac{SSE}{n} \right) + 2p \quad (14)$$

where p and n represent the number of independent variables and observations. And the residual normality of the model can be checked using the Quantile-Quantile QQ plots computed as follows:

$$Q_{y_i} < \tau | x > = \beta_0 + \beta_i x_i + F_u^{-1}(\tau) \quad (15)$$

where Q_{y_i} is response variable conditional value and F_u the error common distribution function given τ .

2.6 Aerosol Particles Radiative Forcing

The knowledge of atmospheric aerosol particles loading is important as it can change the weather and climate patterns by perturbing the radiation budget over any region. Top of the atmosphere TOA and surface radiative forcing are defined as the perturbation in the upscattered solar radiation flux F_{up} and surface reaching solar intensity F_{down} , respectively, with change in the AOD. The surface radiative forcing has been calculated from the following equation (Charlson et al., 1992):

$$F_{Surf} = -0.5 F_T T^2 (1 - A_c) (1 - \bar{R}_s) \bar{\beta} \tau \quad (16)$$

where:

F_T is the solar constant 1370 W/m²,

T is surface temperature,

A_c is the fractional cloud cover,

\bar{R}_s is the mean albedo of the underlying surface,

$\bar{\beta}$ is the fraction of the radiation scattered upward by the aerosol column and

τ is the aerial mean optical depth of the aerosol.

The TOA forcing has been estimated using the CERES Earth radiation budget data and the AOD data from MODIS data. The clear-sky TOA shortwave flux from the CERES has been taken as an estimate of cloud-free aerosol forcing F_{AER} over dusty areas, while the aerosol-free estimates of F_{CLR} come from the observations of the CERES (Christopher and Zhang, 2002). Then the TOA forcing is given as:

$$F_{TOA} = F_{CLR} - F_{AER} \quad (17)$$

where:

F_{CLR} is aerosol free flux estimate,

F_{AER} is the flux estimate over aerosol laden areas.

The atmospheric forcing is given by the difference between TOA and surface:

$$F_{Atm} = F_{TOA} - F_{Surf} \quad (18)$$

The net atmospheric forcing is converted into heat inside the layers containing the absorbing particles, which results in an increase in their temperature and alters the regional climate. Using the basic laws of thermodynamics, the derivation of the temporal rate of this increase is straight-forward, as given by (Ramanathan et al., 2007; Pilewskie, 2007; Liou, 2002):

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{g}{C_p} \frac{\Delta F}{\Delta P} \quad (19)$$

where:

T is the temperature in Kelvin,

t is the time in seconds,

g is the gravitational acceleration,

C_p is the specific heat capacity at constant pressure, and

ΔP is the height of the column containing the aerosol particles expressed as the difference of atmospheric pressure between its bottom and top.

3 Results and Discussion

After extracting the HDF datasets and collecting their spatial raster AOD, AWV, CFM, CTP, and CTT array values from MODIS, PPT array values from TRMM 3B43, and OLR array values from CERES during January 2001–December 2022, the AET values were calculated from the AOD values using the formula described in the methodology Section 2.3. We also perform the AOD combined temporal correlation variation with all parameters and the spatial correlation with the parameters from MODIS Satellite. This section presents the results with their corresponding appropriate discussions for 16 selected sites clustered into four regions, i.e., southwest, southeast, northwest, and northeast of the study area. In addition, we discuss the multiple linear regression analysis and TOA-surface radiative forcing in this section.

3.1 Spatial Correlation

Generally, the East African-Ethiopian climate has been categorized into four major seasons: during December–February the winter in Amharic Bega season; during March–May the spring in Amharic Tseday season; during June–August the summer in Amharic Kiremt season; and during September–November the autumn in Amharic Belg season (Makokha et al., 2017; Aga, 2023; Ayanlade et al., 2019; Kalisa et al., 2023). In this section, respectively from right to left Bega, Tseday, Kiremt, Belg and Annual, we presented the seasonal as well as the total annual average spatial correlation distribution variations for the study periods 2001–2022. The spatial correlation distribution fluctuations of the parameters we observed in these research findings are shown using Figures 2 and 3, for the Terra and Aqua satellite data, respectively. Our observations show that a

slight variation ranges between -1.0 and 1.0. They include the research findings that contain a correlation of AOD with: the Ångström Exponent COA, 1st upper panels, the atmospheric water vapor COW, 2nd panels, the cloud fraction COF, 3rd panels, the cloud top pressure COP, 6th panels, and the cloud top temperature COT (lower panels) over the globe we take the study area {3–18° N, 24–48° E} regions with in it.

- 240 From both the seasonality and total annual results, we can observe that the correlations of the parameters are generally oriented towards the western part of the study area regions, mostly in the southwest of the study area regions. The seasonality distribution variation shows that the minimum values are found in the Bega season, 1st column panels, and the maximum values are in the Kiremt season, 3rd column panels. The Belg season, 4th column panels, is the next to have minimum values, while the next maximum values for the Kiremt season are in the Tesday season, 2nd column panels, for both of the Terra and Aqua instruments.
- 245 The results are similar to the findings of the studies from the Taklimakan desert in China (Li et al., 2014) and the Nile River Basin in Ethiopia (Getachew et al., 2020) while they contradict the observations of the studies at four selected sites: Addis Ababa, Debre Markos, and Debre Tabor in Ethiopia, and Djibouti in Djibouti (Homa et al., 2017; Eshet and Raju, 2022). In the case of the instruments, greater values are observed from the Aqua instrument and less from the Terra instrument, which contradicts the observations in (Kharol et al., 2011).
- 250 So, we can generalize, that the findings in our observations show that the correlations of the parameters have the seasonal minimums in the Bega season and the maximums in the Kiremt season, and the spatial correlations have the minimums mostly in 33–42°E and the maximums in the southwest of the study area regions, respectively. And the correlations of the parameters are higher on the Terra instrument relative to the Aqua instrument. Even if there are also contradictory findings to our results, the studies undergone by different scholars we discussed above and those in (Kalisa et al., 2023; Boiyo et al., 2018) about the
- 255 seasonality of the correlations of the parameters fluctuation, the different local activities, and the long-range aerosol particles transport to the study area regions confirmed our observation (Torres-Delgado et al., 2021; Li et al., 2014; Ngaina et al., 2014).

3.2 Temporal Correlation

This section of the study depicts the results of the total monthly temporal values fluctuations for the aerosol particles, cloud parameters, precipitation, and outgoing long-wave radiation flux we described before. The temporal combined monthly mean

260 values of the parameters are constructed for each site in the four clustered regions. The results of our observations for the parameters combined with AOD values are illustrated in Figures 4 and 5 for the Terra and Aqua satellite data, respectively. Here, in Figures 4 and 5, the increase and decrease fluctuations for the parameters AET, AWV, CFM and PPT are gently positively associated with AOD, while for OLR, CTP and CTT they are vice-versa!

In the southwest cluster, 1st column panels, the minimum values for the parameters are observed in South Sudan at the Raga site,

265 while the maximum values are observed in Ethiopia at the Agnuak site for AOD, AET, CFM, CTP, and CTT; in South Sudan at the Juba site for AWV; and at the Raga site for PPT and OLR. For the southeast cluster, 2nd column panels, the minimum values are observed in Ethiopia at the Kebri Dahar site for AOD, AET, CFM, and PPT. The other minimas in Ethiopia are at the Addis Ababa site for AWV, OLR, CTP, and CTT. And the maximum values are observed in Ethiopia at the Addis Ababa site for AOD, AET, and PPT, and still in Ethiopia at the Kebri Dahar site for AWV, OLR, CTP, and CTT. Another maximum

270 value is observed in Eritrea at the Aseb site for CFM. Here, the results we observed and discussed in the southern clustered regions are from both the Terra and Aqua satellite instruments.

In the northwest cluster, 3rd column panels, minimum values for the parameters are observed in the Ethiopian at the Humera site for AOD, AET, CFM, PPT, OLR, and CTT. The other minima in Ethiopia are at the Dangote sites for AWV and at the Bahir Dar site for CPT. And the maximum values for the parameters are observed in Ethiopia at the Bahir Dar site for AOD, 275 AET, and PPT and at the Humera sites for OLR. The other maxima values for the parameters are observed in South Sudan at the Tonga site for AWV, CFM, CPT, and CTT. When we moved to the northeast cluster, 4th column panels, the minimum values for the parameters were observed in Ethiopia at the Kombolcha site for AOD, AET, AWV, OLR, CTP, and CTT. The other minimum values for the parameters were observed in Djibouti at the Djibouti site for CFM and in Eritrea at the Dahlak site for PPT. And the maximum values for the parameters are observed in Eritrea at the Aseb site for AOD, AET and CFM and at 280 the Dahlak site for CPT and CTT. The other maximum values for the parameters are observed in Djibouti at the Djibouti site for AWV and OLR, and also in Ethiopia at the Kombolcha site for PPT. Here, the results we observed and discussed in the northern clustered regions are from both the Terra and Aqua satellite instruments, with some exceptions. Minimum values for the parameters are observed for OLR at the Bahir Dar and the Ethiopian Renaissance Dam sites, and maximum values for CTP and CTT at the Tonga site in the Aqua satellite.

285 In general, for both of the Terra and Aqua instruments: the minimum values are found at the Kebri Dahar site for both ADD and AET, at the Kombolcha site for AWV, at the Humera site for both CFM and PPT, they all in January and December, while their maximum values are AOD and AET at the Aseb site, AWV at the Tonga site, CFM at the Agnuak site, and PPT at the Bahir Dar site, they all in July; the minimum values were found for OLR at the Humera site and CTP at the Bahir Dar site both in August and CTT at the Raga site in March and April, while the maximum OLR value is at the Kebri Dahar site in 290 February; the maximum CTP value is at the Dahlak site in January and December; the maximum CTT value is at the Dahlak site in November. Exceptionally, the minimum values for the OLR are at the Bahir Dar and Ethiopian Renaissance Dam sites in July and August for the Terra and Aqua instruments, respectively.

3.3 Aerosols Radiative Forcing

To understand aerosol particles loading on regional radiation flux distribution, we have carried out numerical aerosol particles radiative forcing calculations. The total monthly, seasonal and yearly temporal averages of the top of the atmosphere TOA with 295 their corresponding surface radiative forcing values were obtained using the formula in Section 2.6 from the above-mentioned parameters. In the upcoming subsections 3.3.1, 3.3.2 and 3.3.3, we present these results with their appropriate brief discussions.

3.3.1 Monthly Radiative Forcing

In this subsection, the Figures in 6a-6d are to illustrate the results for the aerosol particles, surface in 1st and 3rd row panels 300 as well as atmospheric in 2nd and 4th row panels, radiative forcing. The monthly mean values are constructed based on the F_{Surf} from AOD and F_{TOA} from OLR parameters for each site of the four clustered regions, and the results are illustrated in the Figures. In the southwest cluster (Fig. 6a), the minimum values are observed in South Sudan, at the Juba site for F_{Surf} and at

the Raga site for F_{TOA} , while the maximum values are observed still in South Sudan, both at the Raga site from Terra and Aqua instruments. For the southeast cluster (Fig. 6b), the minimum values are observed in Ethiopia, at the Kebri Dahar site for F_{Surf} and at the Awassa site for F_{TOA} , and the maximum values are observed still in Ethiopia, at the Awassa site for F_{Surf} and at the Addis Ababa site for F_{TOA} , from Terra and Aqua instruments.

For the northwest cluster, Fig. 6c, minimum F_{Surf} and F_{TOA} values are observed in Ethiopia, both at the Bahir Dar site, while maximum values are observed at the Humera site for F_{Surf} in Ethiopia and at the Tonga site in South Sudan for F_{TOA} , from Terra and Aqua instruments. And when we move to the northeast cluster, Fig. 6d, their minimums are in Djibouti at the Djibouti site for F_{Surf} and in Ethiopia at Kombolcha the site for F_{TOA} , while their maximum values are in Ethiopia at the Kombolcha site for F_{Surf} and in Eritrea at the Dahlak site for F_{TOA} , from Terra and Aqua instruments.

To generalize, the minimum values observed are in the northwest cluster for F_{Surf} and in the southeast cluster for F_{TOA} , while the maximum values for F_{Surf} are in the northeast and for F_{TOA} in the northwest cluster from both instruments. For the Terra satellite, the minimum values of F_{Surf} and F_{TOA} were found to be -39.17 and 1.01 in July and December, while the maximum values were to be -0.22 and 109.30 in January and July. Moreover, the Aqua satellite also shows similar results, with the minimum F_{Surf} and F_{TOA} values observed during July and December with -36.56 and 1.17, respectively, while the maximum values in October and August at the two clusters (Fig. 6(b, d)) are -0.64 and 93.80. From the Figures, we can observe that the minimum values are at the Bahir Dar site for F_{Surf} and at the Awassa site for F_{TOA} , both in Ethiopia, while the maximum values are in Ethiopia at the Kombolcha site for F_{Surf} and for F_{TOA} at the Tonga site in South Sudan.

3.3.2 Seasonal Radiative Forcing

The seasonal variations of the radiative forcing parameters F_{Surf} and F_{TOA} at the selected sites clustered into four areas are addressed in this section. The evolutions of these parameters estimated from the study periods of 2001–2022 are shown in Figures 7 for the Terra and Aqua satellite data together with their corresponding total average means. In addition, Tables 3 and 4 also illustrate the seasonal observation of the radiative forcing parameters. Respectively, the minimum values for the parameters F_{Surf} and F_{TOA} are found in the Kiremt and Bega seasons, and their maximum values are found in the Bega and Kiremt seasons, which are in the vice-versa in all of the clusters and both of the instruments.

In the southwest cluster, minimum values for the parameters are observed in South Sudan at the Juba site for F_{Surf} and at the Raga site for F_{TOA} , while the maximum values are observed in South Sudan at the Raga site. For the southeast cluster, the minimum values are observed in Ethiopia at the Kebri Dahar site for F_{Surf} and at the Awassa site for F_{TOA} , and the maximum values are observed in Ethiopia at the Awassa site for F_{Surf} and at the Addis Ababa site for F_{TOA} . Here, the results we observed and discussed in the southern clustered regions are from both the Terra and Aqua satellite instruments.

In the northwest cluster, minimum values for the parameters are observed in Ethiopia at the Bahir Dar site for F_{Surf} and at the Ethiopia Renaissance Dam site for F_{TOA} , and the maximum values for the parameters are observed in Ethiopia at the Humera site for F_{Surf} and in South Sudan at the Tonga site for F_{TOA} . When we moved to the northeast cluster, the minimum values for the parameters were observed in Djibouti at the Djibouti site for F_{Surf} and in Ethiopia at the Kombolcha site for F_{TOA} , and the maximum values for the parameters were observed in Ethiopia at the Kombolcha site for F_{Surf} in Eritrea and at the Dahlak

site for F_{TOA} . Here, the results we observed and discussed in the northern clustered regions are from both the Terra and Aqua satellite instruments, with the exception that the maximum values of F_{TOA} are observed in Ethiopia at the Dangote site.

In general, for both Terra and Aqua instruments, the minimum values found at the Bahir Dar site for F_{Surf} are -34.16 and -32.41
340 in the northwest cluster, at the Awassa site for F_{TOA} are -4.88 and -4.72 in the southwest cluster, while the maximum values found at the Komolcha site for F_{Surf} are -0.30 and -0.22 in the northeast cluster, and for F_{TOA} are around 97.27 at the Tonga site and 92.78 at the Dangote site in the northwest cluster. And the two Tables 3 and 4 are for atmospheric forcing F_{Atm} and its heat rate T_{Rate} calculated using Terra and Aqua instruments. The minimum values found at the Kombolcha site for F_{Atm} are -4.73 and 3.26; for T_{Rate} are 0.0002 and 0.0001; they are all in the southwest cluster, while the maximum values found at the Tonga
345 site for F_{Atm} are 110.65 and 96.13; and for T_{Rate} are around 0.0036 and 0.0031; all are in the northwest cluster.

Those minimums for F_{Surf} , F_{Atm} , T_{Rate} , and the maximums for F_{TOA} are during the Bega season, while those minimums for F_{TOA} , maximums for F_{Surf} , F_{Atm} , and T_{Rate} are during the Kiremt season. Therefore, almost all of the results indicate extreme values at similar locales, like those of the observations in Figures 6, with a few noted exceptions. The results are similar to the findings and the reasons in the study (Liu et al., 2021) from eastern China. The seasonal results for the parameters were similar
350 to those of the observations made in Austria (Yang et al., 2021), Algeria (Khan et al., 2021), eastern China (Liu et al., 2021), and Hong Kong (Yu et al., 2022), despite the fact that there had been no prior studies on the sites in the clustered regions. The discrepancies we discovered were in the minimums with different data periods and site selections. Furthermore, in the study conducted by (Yu et al., 2022) the minimums were primarily at Bega and the maximums at the Kiremt seasons.

3.3.3 Yearly Radiative Forcing

355 In this section, we summarize the total yearly variations of the aerosol particles radiative forcing parameters F_{Surf} and F_{Atm} for all the selected sites belonging to the four clustered regions. The first panel in the error bar Figures 8a indicates the yearly variations for the parameters F_{Surf} from the Terra and Aqua satellites, and the second panel represents the same with the F_{Atm} parameters corresponding to the selected sites in the southwest cluster, and the average of all the sites is also superimposed on all plots. Similarly, Figures 8b-8d produce yearly variations of the F_{Surf} and F_{Atm} parameters for the remaining three clustered
360 regions. The majority of the sites, both in the western and eastern cluster zones, clearly demonstrate interannual variability with frequent minimum and maximum values for parameters, as repeated in the aforementioned figures.

The average of the clustered regions shows minima in 2012 at the southwest cluster for all F_{Surf} and at the southeast cluster for F_{TOA} , with their maxima at the northwest cluster in 2022 for F_{Surf} and in 2010 for F_{TOA} from both instruments. Accordingly, the minimum values are -23.83 and 8.37 for Terra and -22.95 and 7.68 for Aqua, and the maxima are -0.58 and 63.80 for Terra
365 and -1.37 and 58.83 for Aqua, respectively. Here, the values for all of the parameters we observed in the Terra satellite are mostly greater than those of the Aqua satellite. The values for the parameters were higher in the southern clusters, specifically in the southwest clusters, than in the northern clusters.

3.4 Multiple Linear Regression

The performance of selected satellite-derived aerosol particles, clouds, outgoing long-wave radiation flux, and precipitation dataset parameters was evaluated over East Africa-Ethiopia. In this study, the multiple linear regression analysis we discussed in Section 2.5 was carried out for each season based on variables with higher factor loading for the Terra and Aqua instruments. Here, the regression equations for the instruments are expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{AOD} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{AET} + \beta_2\text{AWV} + \beta_3\text{CFM} + \beta_4\text{PPT} + \beta_5\text{OLR} + \beta_6\text{CTP} + \beta_7\text{CTT} \text{ for Terra,} \\ \text{AOD} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{AET} + \beta_2\text{AWV} + \beta_3\text{CFM} + \beta_4\text{OLR} + \beta_5\text{CTP} + \beta_6\text{CTT} \text{ for Aqua instruments.} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Tables 1 and 2 present the results for the 16 chosen sites clustered into four regions, calculated using equation 20 for the Terra and Aqua instruments, respectively. In these tables, the mean cloud fraction CFM was less dominant, while the Ångström exponent AET was the most dominant variable with $0.02733 < \beta_1 < 15.17547$ in the regression equation. The study area regions showed the best performance values with $0.93941 < R < 0.99958$ for all the seasons.

In the Bega season, the performance $0.97064 < R < 0.99928$ and dominance AET $0.04351 < \beta_1 < 5.17874$ values are observed relatively minimally in Ethiopia at the Kombelcha site from Terra and Aqua satellites. Their maximum values are observed in Djibouti at the Djibouti site for the performance and in South Sudan at the Juba site for the dominance variables from both instruments. For the Tseday season, the minimum $0.99001 < R < 0.99958$ and AET $0.80674 < \beta_1 < 7.86178$ values are still observed at the Kombolcha site, and the maximum values are observed at the Awassa site of Ethiopia for the performance and at the Juba site of South Sudan for the dominance of both instruments.

In the Kiremt season, the performance $0.98531 < R < 0.99865$ and dominant AET $3.11914 < \beta_1 < 15.17547$ values are observed relatively minimally in Ethiopia at the Kombolcha site from the Terra and Aqua satellites. Their maximum values are also observed in Ethiopia at the Bahir Dar site from both instruments. For the Belg, the minimum $0.97341 < R < 0.99944$ and AET $0.79291 < \beta_1 < 6.62179$ values are still observed at the Kombolcha site, and the maximum values are observed at the Awassa site of Ethiopia for the performance and at the Juba site of South Sudan for the dominance from both instruments. Here, the performance and dominance of our results are better than in other studies such as (Symeonidis, 2017; Ngaina, 2015), respectively, where they were undergone over Europe and East Africa for PM 2.5.

4 Conclusions

The purpose of this research is to investigate the radiative forcing of aerosol particles and the correlation with precipitation and cloud parameters based on the spatiotemporal distribution variations. They are retrieved from the MODIS, TRMM 3B43, and CERES sensors over a period of 22 years (for Terra: January 2001 to December 2022, and for Aqua: July 2002 to December 2022). Those parameter retrievals included the spatial, temporal, monthly, seasonal and yearly values at sixteen selected sites clustered in four regions with their corresponding averages. The main conclusions drawn from our work are as follows:

1. The seasonal total spatial correlations show slight variations ranging between -1.0 and 1.0. They have minimums in the Bega season and maximums in the Kiremt season; their minimums are mostly in 33–42°E and maximums in the southwest of the study area regions {3–18° N, 24–48° E}, across the globe, we consider the study area regions within it.
2. Minimum values for temporal correlations are found at Kebri Dahar for ADD and AET, at Kombolcha for AWV, and at Humera for CFM and PPT, all in January and December. Their maximums are AOD and AET at Aseb, AWV at Tonga, CFM at Agnuak, and PPT at Bahir Dar, all in July. Minimum OLR values were found at Humera and CTP at Bahir Dar, both in August, and CTT at Raga in March and April. Their maximum OLR value is at Kebri Dahar in February; the maximum CTP value is at Dahlak in January and December; and the maximum CTT value is at Dahlak in November. The minimum values for the OLR are at the Bahir Dar and Ethiopian Renaissance Dam sites in July and August for the Terra and Aqua instruments, respectively.
3. The minimum monthly radiative forcing values observed are in the northwest cluster for F_{Surf} and in the southeast cluster for F_{TOA} , while the maximum values for F_{Surf} are in the northeast and for F_{TOA} in the northwest cluster from both instruments. For the Terra satellite, the minimum values of F_{Surf} and F_{TOA} were found to be -39.17 and 1.01 in July and December, while the maximum values were to be -0.22 and 109.30 in January and July. Moreover, the Aqua satellite also shows similar results, with the minimum F_{Surf} and F_{TOA} values observed during July and December, -36.56 and 1.17, respectively, while the maximum values in October and August at the two clusters are -0.64 and 93.80. The minimum values are at Bahir Dar for F_{Surf} and at Awassa for F_{TOA} , both in Ethiopia, while the maximum values are in Ethiopia at Kombolcha for F_{Surf} and for F_{TOA} at Tonga in South Sudan.
4. The minimum seasonal radiative forcing values found at Bahir Dar for F_{Surf} are -34.16 and -32.41 in the northwest cluster, at Awassa for F_{TOA} are -4.88 and -4.72 in the southwest cluster, while the maximum values found at Kombolcha for F_{Surf} are -0.30 and -0.22 in the northeast cluster, and for F_{TOA} are around 97.27 at Tonga and 92.78 at Dangote in the northwest cluster. The minimum values found at Kombolcha for F_{Atm} are -4.73 and 3.26; for T_{Rate} are 0.0002 and 0.0001; they are all in the southwest cluster, while the maximum values found at Tonga site for F_{Atm} are 110.65 and 96.13; and for T_{Rate} are around 0.0036 and 0.0031; all are in the northwest cluster. The minimums for F_{Surf} , F_{Atm} , T_{Rate} , and the maximums for F_{TOA} are during the Bega season, while those minimums for F_{TOA} , maximums for F_{Surf} , F_{Atm} , and T_{Rate} are during the Kiremt season.
5. The total annual average radiative forcing shows the minima in 2012 at the southwest cluster for all F_{Surf} and at the southeast cluster for F_{TOA} . Their maximums are at the northwest cluster in 2022 for F_{Surf} and in 2010 for F_{TOA} from both instruments. The minimum values are -23.83 and 8.37 for Terra and -22.95 and 7.68 for Aqua, and the maximums are -0.58 and 63.80 for Terra and -1.37 and 58.83 for Aqua, respectively. The values for all of the parameters observed from the Terra satellite are mostly greater than those of the Aqua satellite. The values for the parameters were higher in the southern clusters, specifically in the southwest clusters, than in the northern clusters.

430 6. The mean cloud fraction CFM was less dominant, while the Ångström exponent AET was the most dominant variable
with $0.02733 < \beta_1 < 15.17547$ in the regression analysis. The study area regions showed the best performance values, with
435 $0.93941 < R < 0.99958$ for all the seasons. The minimum values observed in Bega at Kombolcha are from Aqua for both
 β_1 and R, while their maximums are from Terra in Kiremt at Bahir Dar for the dominance and in Tseday at Agnuak for
the performance we described.

Code availability. The codes used to create the figures can be made available upon request to the corresponding authors.

Data availability. The MODIS data for this research were retrieved from the Atmosphere Archive and Distribution System Distributed
Active Archive Center LAADS DAAC website <https://ladsweb.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov/search/>; the CERES data to calculate the outgoing
long-wave radiation flux from the website <https://asdc.larc.nasa.gov/data/CERES/ES4/>; and the TRMM 3B43 data to find the precipitation
440 from the website https://daac.gsfc.nasa.gov/datasets/TRMM_3B43_7/summary?keywords=TRMM_3B43_7.

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Figures

Division	Station	Longitude	Latitude
Southwest	Juba[SS]	31.58	04.86
	Agnuak	34.59	08.25
	Raga[SS]	26.04	08.55
Southeast	Awassa	38.48	07.06
	Kebri Dahar	44.26	06.74
	Addis Ababa	38.75	09.03
Northwest	Dangote	38.34	09.42
	Tonga[SS]	31.70	09.56
	Ethiopian Renaissance Dam	35.09	11.23
	Bahir Dar	37.39	11.59
	Humera	36.61	14.29
Northeast	Kombolcha	39.73	11.09
	Djibouti[DJ]	43.00	11.73
	Aseb[ER]	41.98	13.88
	Erta Ale	40.66	13.06
	Dahlak[ER]	40.06	16.33

Figure 1. Latitudinal and longitudinal sites of the study area.

Figure 2. The aerosol optical parameters spatially correlated distribution.

Figure 3. The aerosol optical parameters spatially correlated distribution.

Figure 4. The aerosol optical parameters combined monthly variation.

Figure 5. The aerosol optical parameters combined monthly variation.

Figure 6. The atmospheric and surface radiative forcing monthly variation.

Figure 8. The atmospheric and surface radiative forcing yearly variation.

Table 1: The regression results and evaluation over the study cities and their clusters for Terra.

Sites	JB	AS	KD	AW	RG	AA	DG	TG	KC	ED	DT	BD	AB	AE	HR	DL	SW	SE	NW	NE		
Bega	R	0.99739	0.99861	0.98888	0.99869	0.99840	0.99822	0.99726	0.99751	0.97064	0.99752	0.99928	0.99920	0.99895	0.99825	0.99669	0.98472	0.98537	0.99202	0.93681		
	R ²	0.99479	0.99722	0.97789	0.99737	0.99679	0.99644	0.99454	0.99502	0.94146	0.99505	0.99856	0.99840	0.99789	0.99651	0.98171	0.99338	0.96968	0.97094	0.98410	0.87705	
	B0	-4.82599	-1.95297	-2.90073	-4.49740	-1.81107	-2.17464	-4.53412	-2.14866	0.48206	-2.56203	-3.21710	-4.63629	-2.28891	-3.34429	-1.18192	-2.82471	-5.38677	-2.35195	-3.19372	0.00704	
	B1	5.17874	2.13126	3.64916	4.59315	1.99977	2.16140	4.32406	1.99736	0.04351	2.71170	3.14421	4.79506	2.21971	3.34668	1.63372	2.83708	4.24339	2.77642	2.62163	0.39332	
	B2	-0.00457	-0.00160	-0.00863	-0.00002	-0.00319	-0.00224	-0.00779	0.00107	0.00943	-0.00568	0.00188	-0.00430	-0.00482	-0.00426	0.00751	-0.01237	0.01899	-0.01077	-0.05370	-0.14756	
	B3	0.03020	0.02821	-0.02922	0.00786	-0.02198	-0.01901	0.04255	-0.01927	-0.09768	0.24403	-0.00154	0.00941	-0.00215	0.01522	-0.08669	0.00994	0.01889	-0.01151	0.30959	0.20340	
	B4	0.00397	-0.01120	0.00570	0.00261	0.00462	0.00040	-0.00401	-0.00059	0.00569	0.01227	0.00045	0.00906	-0.00019	0.00337	-0.01559	-0.00443	-0.01086	0.00989	0.00048	0.02865	
	B5	0.00060	0.00005	-0.00110	0.00003	-0.00048	-0.00046	0.00036	-0.00024	-0.00146	-0.00009	-0.00005	0.00022	-0.00022	-0.00001	-0.00078	-0.00035	0.00194	-0.00042	0.00110	-0.00307	
	B6	0.00031	0.00011	0.00032	0.00013	-0.00001	-0.00013	-0.00011	-0.00018	0.00008	0.00006	-0.00003	0.00012	-0.00013	0.00006	0.00006	-0.00008	-0.00033	0.00022	0.00004	-0.00028	
	B7	-0.00352	-0.00080	-0.00248	-0.00129	0.00003	0.00096	0.00020	0.00139	-0.00049	-0.00053	0.00029	-0.00172	0.00093	-0.00024	-0.00075	0.00061	0.00244	-0.00151	0.00112	0.00379	
	R	0.99773	0.99714	0.99672	0.99958	0.99787	0.99782	0.99627	0.99749	0.99001	0.99888	0.99869	0.99811	0.99755	0.99130	0.98267	0.98861	0.99725	0.96305	0.97654	0.98866	0.97207
	R ²	0.99546	0.99428	0.99345	0.99915	0.99573	0.99564	0.99256	0.99498	0.98011	0.99777	0.99739	0.99622	0.99511	0.98267	0.98861	0.99725	0.96305	0.95363	0.97744	0.94491	
	B0	-8.36636	-2.93890	-7.65915	-6.83716	-2.60691	-2.59110	-3.39576	-2.49167	-1.14608	-3.60382	-4.69321	-7.35885	-2.56467	-3.95886	-3.56336	-3.89486	-5.56207	-3.53378	-3.61129	-2.15004	
	B1	7.86178	3.01838	5.66388	6.26897	2.66821	2.50793	3.93878	2.62192	0.80674	3.76093	4.60947	7.12309	2.46779	3.11478	3.35868	4.18626	5.39390	4.07821	3.95822	2.12924	
B2	-0.01314	0.01488	-0.00507	-0.00996	0.00014	0.00317	0.00057	-0.00473	0.00227	0.00191	0.00212	-0.00641	-0.00308	-0.02622	0.01304	-0.00483	-0.01427	-0.02270	-0.02514	-0.00746		
B3	-0.05548	0.00349	0.26575	0.01624	0.01474	0.00365	-0.12629	0.04294	0.00297	-0.02831	-0.01570	0.01829	0.00651	-0.03606	0.00568	-0.05010	0.06933	0.09573	-0.06722	-0.27648		
B4	-0.01155	0.00457	0.01698	-0.00168	0.00175	0.00162	0.00328	0.00126	0.00484	0.00211	-0.00108	-0.00718	0.00143	-0.00254	0.00025	0.00326	0.00545	0.00213	0.01328	0.00291		
B5	0.00039	0.00020	0.00237	0.00000	0.00003	0.00014	-0.00205	-0.00013	0.00002	-0.00041	-0.00009	0.00008	0.00001	-0.00125	0.00028	-0.00072	0.00039	-0.00085	-0.00149	-0.00157		
B6	-0.00010	0.00006	-0.00061	-0.00016	0.00005	-0.00007	0.00030	0.00013	-0.00028	0.00008	0.00005	0.00008	-0.00009	-0.00061	0.00020	0.00015	0.00001	0.00028	-0.00001	-0.00053		
B7	-0.00009	-0.00085	0.00501	0.00130	-0.00036	0.00035	-0.00074	-0.00065	0.00210	-0.00063	-0.00027	-0.00104	0.00062	0.00611	-0.00134	-0.00103	-0.00053	-0.00196	0.00018	0.00348		
R	0.99845	0.99346	0.99543	0.99764	0.99622	0.99614	0.99595	0.99628	0.98531	0.99530	0.99726	0.99865	0.99608	0.99383	0.99291	0.99299	0.99370	0.99449	0.99676	0.99591		
R ²	0.99690	0.98697	0.99088	0.99529	0.99245	0.99230	0.99191	0.99257	0.97083	0.99063	0.99452	0.99729	0.99218	0.98770	0.98586	0.98603	0.98743	0.98901	0.99354	0.98785		
B0	-15.10030	-6.16242	-10.25660	-16.99038	-8.62347	-7.81357	-4.23128	-5.87472	-3.63881	-7.39898	-10.04492	-17.59893	-6.30670	-4.70830	-3.78248	-4.99753	-14.66634	-7.97946	-9.40950	-6.21606		
B1	14.99690	6.67762	8.94890	13.17372	7.41175	6.88324	6.03874	6.48529	3.11914	6.58915	9.07290	15.17547	6.57664	5.54444	4.96162	5.78352	12.05913	7.30048	7.65194	5.80691		
B2	0.00276	-0.05242	-0.02005	0.00912	-0.00389	0.00683	0.02919	0.02120	-0.00591	-0.01316	0.00314	0.00237	0.00400	-0.00366	-0.01235	0.00196	0.01582	-0.02160	0.00406	0.00717		
B3	0.03339	0.33679	0.17652	0.16623	0.00921	0.13045	-0.04651	-0.11712	-0.06242	0.00535	-0.01127	-0.01476	0.02595	0.02214	0.11732	-0.06394	-0.02018	0.09336	-0.01479	-0.23199		
B4	0.00305	0.00863	0.00028	-0.01173	0.00507	0.00460	-0.00187	0.00252	-0.00554	0.00606	0.00057	0.00398	0.00268	0.00270	0.00228	-0.00019	0.00979	0.00362	-0.00664	0.00440		
B5	0.00047	0.00101	0.00015	0.00178	0.00004	0.00120	-0.00043	-0.00076	0.00041	-0.00003	-0.00009	0.00025	-0.00006	0.00001	0.00138	-0.00071	0.00084	0.00031	-0.00061	-0.00136		
B6	0.00063	0.00132	-0.00042	-0.00122	-0.00049	0.00002	0.00171	0.00063	-0.00033	0.00005	-0.00015	-0.00065	0.00060	0.00059	0.00122	0.00057	-0.00082	0.00011	-0.00017	-0.00027		
B7	-0.00808	-0.00686	0.00295	0.00935	0.00353	0.00031	-0.01117	-0.00412	0.00242	0.00176	0.00124	0.00362	-0.00376	-0.00465	-0.00901	-0.00446	0.00603	0.00036	0.00610	0.00280		
R	0.99894	0.99932	0.99638	0.99944	0.99873	0.99902	0.99919	0.99838	0.97341	0.99843	0.99940	0.99923	0.99891	0.99930	0.99864	0.99876	0.99467	0.99235	0.99830	0.96111		
R ²	0.99789	0.99865	0.99278	0.99889	0.99747	0.99804	0.99839	0.99676	0.94753	0.99685	0.99881	0.99846	0.99783	0.99860	0.99728	0.99752	0.98938	0.98475	0.99659	0.92373		
B0	-7.64466	-3.58295	-5.12974	-6.93391	-3.70672	-3.51675	-4.31117	-3.24165	-1.13543	-4.34295	-5.28954	-7.14063	-3.52572	-3.42722	-3.15108	-3.82668	-6.22918	-3.53954	-4.13948	-3.42043		
B1	6.47635	3.41814	5.38812	6.44610	3.68950	3.55209	4.15201	3.36009	0.79291	4.11812	5.08811	6.62179	3.58780	3.34811	3.18343	3.78525	5.54723	4.37965	4.16398	2.00159		
B2	-0.00390	0.00008	-0.01270	0.00389	-0.00058	0.00504	0.00054	0.00044	-0.00171	-0.00251	0.00369	0.00787	-0.00257	0.00119	0.00002	-0.00092	-0.00194	0.00603	-0.01121	-0.00548		
B3	0.04240	0.00363	0.02226	-0.00891	0.02284	0.01875	-0.00582	-0.01581	-0.06870	0.01560	0.00787	0.01826	0.00587	-0.00554	0.00204	0.00629	0.05354	-0.03938	0.03692	0.05230		
B4	-0.00206	-0.00063	-0.00637	-0.00080	0.00055	0.00008	0.00015	0.00053	-0.00127	0.00195	0.00000	-0.00177	0.00032	0.00019	0.00003	0.00029	0.00086	-0.00537	-0.00139	-0.00311		
B5	0.00051	0.00012	0.00045	0.00014	0.00015	0.00039	0.00001	-0.00012	-0.00070	0.00004	0.00029	0.00047	0.00003	-0.00005	0.00005	0.00001	0.00053	0.00036	-0.00003	0.00010		
B6	-0.00037	-0.00006	0.00027	-0.00004	0.00007	0.00010	-0.00004	0.00004	-0.00020	-0.00004	0.00003	0.00000	0.00007	-0.00001	0.00004	0.00003	-0.00022	0.00054	0.00005	-0.00077		
B7	0.00327	0.00045	-0.00282	0.00033	-0.00051	-0.00101	0.00025	-0.00064	0.00274	0.00046	-0.00042	-0.00016	-0.00064	0.00020	-0.00037	-0.00021	0.00154	-0.00054	-0.00050	0.00724		
Kiremt	R	0.99845	0.99346	0.99543	0.99764	0.99622	0.99614	0.99595	0.99628	0.98531	0.99726	0.99865	0.99608	0.99383	0.99291	0.99299	0.99370	0.99449	0.99676	0.99591		
	R ²	0.99690	0.98697	0.99088	0.99529	0.99245	0.99230	0.99191	0.99257	0.97083	0.99452	0.99729	0.99218	0.98770	0.98586	0.98603	0.98743	0.98901	0.99354	0.98785		
	B0	-15.10030	-6.16242	-10.25660	-16.99038	-8.62347	-7.81357	-4.23128	-5.87472	-3.63881	-7.39898	-10.04492	-17.59893	-6.30670	-4.70830	-3.78248	-4.99753	-14.66634	-7.97946	-9.40950	-6.21606	
	B1	14.99690	6.67762	8.94890	13.17372	7.41175	6.88324	6.03874	6.48529	3.11914	6.58915	9.07290	15.17547	6.57664	5.54444	4.96162	5.78352	12.05913	7.30048	7.65194	5.80691	
	B2	0.00276	-0.05242</																			

Table 2: The regression results and evaluation over the study cites and their clusters for Aqaa.

Sites	JB	AS	KD	AW	RG	AA	DG	TG	KC	ED	DT	BD	AB	AE	HR	DL	SW	SE	NW	NE	
Bega	R	0.99845	0.99790	0.99432	0.99778	0.99714	0.99847	0.99749	0.93941	0.99429	0.99900	0.99841	0.99878	0.99531	0.99490	0.99609	0.99110	0.99581	0.99149	0.96469	
	R ²	0.99690	0.99581	0.98868	0.99557	0.99429	0.99693	0.98538	0.99500	0.88109	0.98861	0.99800	0.99682	0.99756	0.99064	0.98982	0.99220	0.98228	0.99163	0.98305	0.93063
	B0	-5.34259	-1.67718	-3.60456	-4.11376	-1.87003	-1.79909	-3.73065	-1.82121	-0.06997	-1.95835	-2.26812	-4.58216	-1.64927	-2.61401	-1.01113	-1.30254	-4.73196	-2.85550	-2.26374	-1.13829
	B1	4.98516	1.84179	3.09732	4.05357	2.03633	1.98948	4.22418	1.84714	0.02733	2.45520	2.37187	4.51833	1.84093	3.01423	1.48000	2.13159	3.56603	2.17247	2.34129	0.45532
	B2	0.01581	0.00283	0.00424	0.00118	0.00349	-0.02565	-0.02255	0.00131	0.00187	0.01131	-0.00607	0.00242	-0.01561	-0.00083	0.01002	0.00151	0.02418	-0.00797	-0.02872	-0.11799
	B3	-0.01354	0.03075	0.06199	-0.01046	0.06577	0.02325	0.06700	-0.04223	-0.01256	0.00043	0.00475	-0.00464	0.01903	-0.00896	-0.04920	-0.05916	0.00456	0.12876	0.26276	0.25464
	B4	0.00124	0.00009	0.00085	0.00019	0.00032	-0.00045	0.00073	-0.00029	-0.00014	-0.00050	-0.00008	0.00011	-0.00035	-0.00016	-0.00052	-0.00111	0.00256	0.00137	0.00146	-0.00081
	B5	-0.00002	0.00010	-0.00015	0.00000	0.00012	-0.00003	0.00012	-0.00017	-0.00014	0.00026	-0.00004	0.00005	0.00000	0.00024	0.00015	0.00027	-0.00044	-0.00016	0.00033	-0.00046
	B6	-0.00077	-0.00076	0.00115	-0.00035	-0.00111	0.00010	-0.00315	0.00083	0.00069	-0.00190	-0.00009	-0.00057	-0.00008	-0.00189	-0.00129	-0.00229	0.00232	0.00152	-0.00245	0.00546
	R	0.99753	0.99753	0.99168	0.99860	0.99836	0.99685	0.99675	0.99832	0.98578	0.99627	0.99870	0.99805	0.99719	0.99091	0.99614	0.99830	0.99578	0.98546	0.99132	0.98167
R ²	0.99507	0.99507	0.98342	0.99719	0.99672	0.99371	0.99350	0.99664	0.97177	0.99255	0.99741	0.99611	0.99439	0.98190	0.99229	0.99661	0.99158	0.97114	0.98271	0.96368	
B0	-7.87869	-2.72318	-8.53618	-5.77910	-2.56453	-2.27902	-2.88333	-2.14561	-0.70641	-3.36053	-3.67454	-7.10334	-2.16669	-2.90725	-2.79396	-3.58520	-4.62322	-5.28573	-3.20552	-3.01507	
B1	7.27081	3.12531	5.99488	5.60832	3.06257	2.44113	3.66860	2.46264	0.89413	3.87065	3.67735	6.82893	3.23231	3.03430	3.40547	3.69811	4.95218	4.43743	3.95971	2.32607	
B2	-0.01505	0.00827	-0.00722	-0.00437	0.00138	-0.00789	-0.00084	-0.00246	0.01068	0.00323	0.00588	-0.00617	-0.00435	-0.04992	0.01393	0.00056	0.00296	0.04885	0.00609	-0.03452	
B3	-0.02039	-0.05512	0.09671	0.00101	0.04269	0.00670	-0.21137	0.02531	-0.03538	-0.00140	0.00837	-0.02337	-0.02900	-0.22280	-0.04698	-0.04224	-0.00993	0.23114	-0.15165	-0.06753	
B4	-0.00036	-0.00088	0.00096	0.00003	0.00003	-0.00026	-0.00193	-0.00039	-0.00012	-0.00033	0.00025	-0.00030	-0.00037	-0.00237	0.00003	-0.00048	0.00153	0.00238	-0.00049	-0.00113	
B5	-0.00013	0.00017	-0.00103	0.00002	0.00043	0.00009	0.00024	0.00025	0.00002	0.00039	0.00007	0.00007	0.00003	-0.00048	0.00045	0.00005	0.00022	0.00021	0.00025	-0.00073	
B6	0.00135	-0.00100	0.00950	-0.00039	-0.00288	-0.00040	-0.00127	-0.00126	-0.00038	-0.00271	-0.00070	-0.00028	-0.00006	0.00393	-0.00348	-0.00025	-0.00395	-0.00087	-0.00295	0.00585	
R	0.99683	0.99281	0.99423	0.99669	0.99504	0.99391	0.99214	0.99479	0.98945	0.99304	0.99611	0.99749	0.99546	0.99273	0.98977	0.99399	0.99525	0.99565	0.99226	0.98998	
R ²	0.99367	0.98567	0.98850	0.99339	0.99010	0.98786	0.98435	0.98960	0.97902	0.98613	0.99224	0.99498	0.99095	0.98550	0.97964	0.98802	0.99053	0.99131	0.98458	0.98006	
B0	-14.45146	-6.54261	-9.90992	-13.81813	-8.17245	-6.32625	-5.45678	-6.11586	-0.92156	-6.58728	-6.57624	-16.10623	-7.01182	-4.37424	-4.34938	-3.85918	-12.88182	-7.42426	-7.87745	-5.06057	
B1	13.62305	6.90159	10.90797	12.65190	7.67963	6.26453	6.04307	6.09746	3.07604	6.61075	7.99529	14.72187	6.64147	5.49976	5.07697	5.52691	12.06861	8.10709	7.41057	5.59690	
B2	0.02169	-0.00894	0.00215	-0.01037	0.00385	-0.01669	0.03923	0.03141	-0.02420	0.00262	0.01650	0.00384	0.04207	-0.01025	-0.00936	-0.02074	0.09199	-0.01499	0.04449	0.02066	
B3	-0.00538	0.05921	-0.08090	0.33905	-0.03561	0.01382	0.01662	-0.21396	-0.13329	0.00092	-0.01122	-0.14617	-0.13910	0.01995	0.03800	0.13046	-0.68010	0.10328	-0.01651	-0.19029	
B4	0.00101	0.00145	0.00075	0.00118	0.00003	-0.00062	0.00102	-0.00058	-0.00179	0.00059	0.00046	0.00001	-0.00090	-0.00045	0.00058	0.00174	0.00005	0.00035	0.00052	-0.00047	
B5	0.00007	0.00068	0.00084	0.00077	0.00028	0.00040	0.00082	0.00011	0.00076	0.00042	0.00158	-0.00011	0.00024	0.00086	0.00087	0.00168	-0.00038	0.00107	0.00039	0.00048	
B6	-0.00377	-0.00561	-0.00991	-0.00372	-0.00058	-0.00110	-0.00654	-0.00043	-0.00729	-0.00291	-0.01109	-0.00052	0.00031	-0.00650	-0.00567	-0.01214	-0.00026	-0.00716	-0.00172	-0.00323	
R	0.99770	0.99949	0.99631	0.99927	0.99868	0.99846	0.99827	0.99638	0.98533	0.99685	0.99902	0.99915	0.99802	0.99943	0.99811	0.99850	0.99792	0.98309	0.99821	0.97083	
R ²	0.99541	0.99897	0.99263	0.99853	0.99736	0.99693	0.99654	0.99277	0.97088	0.99371	0.99804	0.99830	0.99604	0.99885	0.99622	0.99700	0.99585	0.96648	0.99642	0.94251	
B0	-6.33808	-3.49903	-6.02668	-5.74312	-3.73582	-3.19301	-3.87011	-3.06604	-0.90965	-4.04028	-4.00923	-5.86336	-3.39928	-3.35704	-3.76168	-3.62088	-4.09813	-3.78074	-3.41053	-3.51564	
B1	5.79678	3.29637	5.65792	5.61530	3.75735	3.31458	3.97587	3.07842	0.84766	4.02052	3.98536	5.78415	3.30233	3.24009	3.46893	3.77003	4.86638	4.22298	4.10235	2.33306	
B2	-0.00526	-0.00049	-0.00061	0.00399	0.00348	0.00417	-0.00032	0.00421	0.02047	0.00548	0.00349	-0.00175	0.00536	0.00701	-0.00405	0.00594	-0.00331	0.03758	0.00732	0.01675	
B3	0.00680	0.00928	-0.04424	0.01093	0.01353	0.04013	0.00186	0.02075	-0.01174	-0.01185	0.02172	0.02258	0.01337	0.00298	-0.01488	0.01693	0.05853	-0.08807	-0.08348	0.11284	
B4	0.00002	0.00018	0.00008	0.00011	0.00022	0.00033	0.00042	-0.00010	-0.00017	0.00007	0.00046	0.00012	0.00036	0.00028	-0.00038	0.00049	0.00066	0.00090	0.00010	0.00178	
B5	-0.00017	-0.00009	-0.00020	0.00012	0.00010	0.00026	0.00011	0.00010	-0.00002	0.00005	0.00009	0.00010	0.00000	-0.00003	-0.00017	0.00020	0.00058	0.00025	0.00027	-0.00040	
B6	0.00136	0.00064	0.00076	-0.00097	-0.00085	-0.00155	-0.00138	-0.00030	0.00050	-0.00052	-0.00096	-0.00114	-0.00020	0.00002	0.00173	-0.00185	-0.00555	-0.00372	-0.00356	0.00336	

Belg

Kiremt

Tseday

Table 3: The mean atmospheric and surface forcing pattern over the study cities and their clusters for Terra.

Sites	JB	AS	KD	AW	RG	AA	DG	TG	KC	ED	DT	BD	AB	AE	HR	DL	SW	SE	NW	NE
Bega	AF	23.15568	1.41174	14.69848	23.97576	2.64318	12.24470	4.42121	2.64318	7.33750	14.69848	12.73333	16.42727	4.49848	9.78068	16.59154	9.61452	9.67439	10.14000	
	SF	-12.98739	-4.82904	-8.90658	-11.25702	-4.88179	-5.18049	-10.28153	-4.66734	-6.45349	-7.42012	-11.69769	-5.34913	-8.20712	-4.32519	-7.21522	-9.70873	-6.30537	-7.48505	-5.69924
	AT	36.14307	6.24078	23.60507	35.23278	7.52498	17.91382	24.56865	16.91204	4.72582	9.09667	14.75762	26.39617	18.08247	24.63440	16.99590	26.30027	15.91989	17.15944	15.83924
	AR	0.00117	0.00020	0.00077	0.00114	0.00024	0.00058	0.00080	0.00055	0.00015	0.00030	0.00048	0.00086	0.00059	0.00080	0.00055	0.00085	0.00052	0.00056	0.00051
Tseday	AF	13.72121	8.45758	8.27121	20.46212	18.07121	28.20909	44.48182	48.92879	28.12879	18.07121	20.50758	8.27121	28.20909	41.06061	22.43485	35.55303	17.41818	14.97929	30.69182
	SF	-17.18036	-7.38210	-13.59306	-14.32550	-6.31810	-5.92374	-8.89297	-6.28691	-2.14666	-8.54611	-10.72925	-17.23108	-5.98428	-7.57302	-9.61910	-12.60799	-8.96630	-9.69954	-7.21046
	AT	30.90157	15.83968	21.86427	34.78762	24.38931	34.13283	53.36479	55.21569	30.27545	26.61732	31.23682	25.50230	34.19337	48.63363	29.98547	45.17213	30.02617	23.94559	37.90228
	AR	0.00100	0.00051	0.00071	0.00113	0.00079	0.00111	0.00173	0.00179	0.00098	0.00086	0.00101	0.00083	0.00111	0.00158	0.00047	0.00098	0.00078	0.00124	0.00123
Kiremt	AF	21.22576	38.47727	19.80151	21.67727	65.16061	65.62727	97.27273	40.16061	65.16061	53.35000	19.80151	65.62727	52.82576	56.74697	80.28636	36.02121	41.30202	66.35303	58.45000
	SF	-33.73628	-14.54405	-20.60127	-30.54413	-15.16106	-14.19050	-11.44491	-13.38030	-6.88048	-13.20017	-19.98690	-34.15932	-14.07675	-10.98041	-11.74704	-26.48049	-16.44527	-16.30557	-12.73432
	AT	54.96204	53.02132	40.40278	52.22140	80.32167	79.81778	104.22825	110.65302	47.04108	78.42078	73.33690	53.96804	79.70403	63.80617	66.03013	62.50170	57.74729	82.65860	71.18432
	AR	0.00178	0.00172	0.00131	0.00170	0.00261	0.00259	0.00338	0.00359	0.00153	0.00255	0.00238	0.00175	0.00259	0.00207	0.00214	0.00299	0.00203	0.00188	0.00231
Belg	AF	8.99697	10.40000	5.96818	14.48939	24.77576	30.31061	49.95606	62.06061	28.06667	24.77576	23.77121	5.96818	30.31061	38.68636	26.78333	41.81515	16.08737	15.55960	32.53000
	SF	-15.25620	-7.73995	-12.17285	-14.85048	-8.39881	-8.01339	-9.56743	-7.74162	-2.00247	-9.05740	-11.53194	-15.36782	-8.14831	-7.52669	-8.54390	-12.83516	-9.30873	-9.81585	-7.55066
	AT	24.25317	18.13995	18.14103	29.33988	33.17456	38.32399	59.52349	69.80222	30.06913	33.83316	35.30315	21.33600	38.45891	46.21305	34.12830	50.35905	28.92254	24.86833	40.08066
	AR	0.00079	0.00059	0.00059	0.00095	0.00108	0.00124	0.00193	0.00227	0.00098	0.00110	0.00115	0.00069	0.00125	0.00150	0.00164	0.00094	0.00081	0.00142	0.00130

Table 4: The mean atmospheric and surface forcing pattern over the study cities and their clusters for Aqua.

Sites	JB	AS	KD	AW	RG	AA	DG	TG	KC	ED	DT	BD	AB	AE	HR	DL	SW	SE	NW	NE	
Bega	AF	18.30952	1.70952	11.44286	16.27460	6.06825	15.73175	12.98571	14.06349	3.04762	6.06825	11.51429	11.44286	15.73175	23.32540	7.63810	13.55079	9.62804	9.93714	12.25143	
	SF	-11.90889	-4.00077	-7.70810	-9.71521	-4.71818	-4.70498	-10.45702	-4.27969	-0.21723	-5.78479	-5.58341	-10.71906	-4.41376	-7.70609	-3.46934	-5.49113	-8.78076	-5.47129	-6.94198	-4.68232
	AT	30.21841	5.71030	19.15096	25.98981	10.78644	20.43673	23.44274	18.34318	3.26485	11.85304	17.09770	22.16192	20.14550	31.03148	8.59473	13.12922	22.33155	15.09933	16.87912	16.93375
	AR	0.00098	0.00019	0.00062	0.00084	0.00035	0.00066	0.00076	0.00060	0.00011	0.00038	0.00056	0.00072	0.00065	0.00101	0.00028	0.00043	0.00073	0.00049	0.00055	0.00055
Tseday	AF	10.96000	10.86167	9.19500	18.55833	27.93667	41.72500	43.53167	47.12500	19.21833	27.93667	37.47333	9.19500	41.72500	53.00000	27.16000	37.57833	19.15167	20.59389	37.79900	
	SF	-15.98806	-6.90777	-14.70560	-13.08689	-7.06127	-5.74008	-8.84596	-5.87609	-2.52002	-8.93310	-8.58990	-16.18343	-5.55332	-7.24664	-7.48014	-8.65557	-12.04541	-9.11781	-9.46374	-6.51309
	AT	26.94806	17.76943	23.90060	31.64522	34.99794	47.46508	52.37763	53.00109	21.73836	36.86977	46.06323	25.37843	47.27832	60.24664	34.64014	46.23390	31.19707	29.71170	40.45341	44.31209
	AR	0.00088	0.00058	0.00078	0.00103	0.00114	0.00154	0.00170	0.00172	0.00071	0.00120	0.00150	0.00082	0.00154	0.00196	0.00112	0.00150	0.00101	0.00096	0.00131	0.00144
Kiremt	AF	16.54444	39.42857	17.04127	18.85476	68.24444	65.68810	84.83571	82.41905	35.50635	68.24444	67.20397	17.04127	65.68810	62.24524	55.60794	83.12222	34.54788	40.71931	61.62968	62.75317
	SF	-31.79153	-14.37704	-24.41206	-29.39749	-16.01486	-13.14576	-11.29856	-11.87908	-6.46762	-13.58314	-17.91042	-32.41897	-13.59654	-10.87027	-8.95797	-10.65410	-25.73463	-17.31162	-15.62754	-11.90099
	AT	48.33598	53.80561	41.45333	48.25225	84.25931	78.83385	96.13427	94.29813	41.97396	81.82758	85.11438	49.46024	79.28463	73.12151	64.56591	93.77632	60.28251	58.03093	77.25723	74.65416
	AR	0.00157	0.00175	0.00135	0.00157	0.00274	0.00256	0.00312	0.00306	0.00136	0.00266	0.00276	0.00161	0.00257	0.00237	0.00210	0.00305	0.00196	0.00188	0.00251	0.00242
Belg	AF	7.35635	12.75079	9.87063	14.02381	34.40635	38.61191	49.62698	57.32540	19.71270	34.40635	33.06905	9.87063	38.61191	49.34762	28.33095	42.41746	18.59550	20.41111	35.91206	36.63175
	SF	-13.21147	-7.56710	-12.66958	-12.77111	-8.47623	-7.39614	-9.28202	-7.02963	-2.22285	-8.84136	-8.89064	-13.54952	-7.32019	-7.47655	-7.59316	-8.15845	-11.48627	-9.21094	-9.25914	-6.81374
	AT	20.56782	20.31789	22.54022	26.79491	42.88258	46.00804	58.90900	64.35503	21.93555	43.24771	41.95969	23.42015	45.93210	56.82417	35.92412	50.57591	30.08177	29.62205	45.17120	43.44548
	AR	0.00067	0.00066	0.00073	0.00087	0.00139	0.00149	0.00191	0.00209	0.00071	0.00140	0.00136	0.00076	0.00149	0.00185	0.00117	0.00164	0.00098	0.00096	0.00147	0.00141